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www.ggos.org/event/ggos-days-2024/

Status report of the GGOS organisational components

30 September 2024

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Foreword

It is our pleasure to present the report of the GGOS Components prepared for the GGOS Days 2024. This year has been one of resilience, growth and innovation for the GGOS community. As is customary within the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG), the parent organisation of the International Association of Geodesy (IAG), GGOS renews the membership of its Governing Board (GB) every four years. The GGOS Governing Board is the central oversight and decision-making body of GGOS and the collective voice for all GGOS matters, as it is composed of one representative from each of the IAG Components and the Chairs of the organisational elements of GGOS. This Board is responsible for the governance, strategic policy and direction of GGOS. For the period 2023-2027, the GGOS-GB is composed of 45 voting members and 10 non-voting members. They are from 20 countries: Argentina, Australia, Austria, Czech Republic, People's Republic of China, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, India, Iran, Japan, Netherlands, Poland, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom and United States of America. 18 members are women and 27 are early career scientists. This renewal ensures the flow of fresh ideas and new impetus to take GGOS forward.

The GGOS Executive Committee (EC), which is responsible for the day-to-day activities of GGOS, with the support of the GGOS-GB and the GGOS Science Panel, developed a new Strategic Plan for the period 2024-2034 and the corresponding Implementation Plan for the period 2024-2027. The new GGOS Strategic and Implementation Plans were unanimously approved by the GGOS-GB on 25 January 2024 and 18 September 2024, respectively. These two plans chart the way forward for GGOS and provide a well-thought-out framework for addressing the key challenges facing GGOS.

The present document summarises the progress and planned actions for the next year of the different Operational Components and Focus Areas of GGOS, namely the GGOS Coordinating Office, the Bureau of Networks and Observations, the Bureau of Products and Standards, and the Focus Areas on Geohazards Monitoring, Geodetic Space Weather Research and Artificial Intelligence for Geodesy. Throughout the document you will see line by line the great work behind each Component and share our pride in this collective effort, all based on the voluntary collaboration of every colleague involved in GGOS.

In addition to the achievements summarised in the sessions of this document, we would like to highlight the following:

Definition of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs): The Chair of the GGOS Committee on EGVs, the Director of the BPS and the GGOS President have prepared a White Paper with an approach to the definition of EGVs. The main goal is to describe the contribution of geodesy to Earth observation using the same language as other global observing systems such as the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) or the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS). This will increase the visibility of geodesy and the usability of its

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products for the benefit of other sciences and society. The present concept considers 18 EGVs based on 53 geodetic products. The EGVs are divided into the domains Global (for the whole Earth), Land and Ocean. The sub-domain indicates whether the EGV relates to the geometry or the gravity field of the Earth. This concept has been reviewed and endorsed by the GGOS Science Panel and is currently under review by the GGOS Governing Board. Once the feedback from the GGOS Governing Board has been incorporated into the White Paper, we will present it to the IAG Executive Committee members for further review. Once the concept has been accepted/approved/endorsed by the IAG Executive Committee, we will launch a dissemination and consultation exercise with the global geodetic community to achieve a general consensus.

Establishment of a new GGOS Affiliate: GGOS IberAtlantic. GGOS Affiliates are national or regional geodesy-related organisations that facilitate greater collaboration across regions, communities and new technologies. Fostering regional alliances is a powerful tool to identify, enable and develop sustained geodetic observations, products and services following regional and national priorities, aligned with the global goals of GGOS. GGOS IberAtlantic joins the two existing Affiliates GGOS Japan and GGOS-DACH (for Germany, Austria and Switzerland).

Fostering multidisciplinary research: GGOS is leading a joint initiative between IAG and the International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA) to establish a multidisciplinary network of scientists to integrate geodetic and geophysical technologies for comprehensive monitoring of the Magnetosphere, Ionosphere, Plasmasphere and Thermosphere as a coupled system. To this end, we prepared the project *“Characterisation of the ionised atmosphere in terms of essential variables”*, which has been approved in the frame of the IUGG Grants Programme 2024 – 2025. This project is the main support for the GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere, held in conjunction with the GGOS Days 2024 in Potsdam, Germany, in October 2024.

GGOS interaction with the UN Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence (UN-GGCE): The GGOS Coordinating Office and the UN-GGCE have regular monthly meetings to report and agree on outreach activities. Recently, a joint short video on reference frames, based on previous GGOS videos, was jointly released. The GGOS BPS and BNO support UN-GGCE activities related to the survey of needs and challenges of IAG services as input for the Global Geodesy Needs Assessment. The GGOS Executive Committee completed a survey on the GGOS contribution (according to the GGOS Implementation Plan) to the First Joint Global Geodesy Development Plan. GGOS input was included in the IAG contribution to this plan.

Joint Commission 2, IGFS and GGOS Symposium GGHS2024 (Gravity, Geoid and Height Systems 2024), 4-6 September 2024: For the first time, GGOS was a direct co-organiser of a Gravity Symposium. In addition to participating in the definition of the scientific programme of the meeting, GGOS had the opportunity to present several GGOS topics in detail, which undoubtedly contributed to promote the GGOS activities within the gravity field community.

Geodesy in Africa at the UN Science Summit and towards GGOS Africa. Thanks to the initiative of our colleague Aletha de Witt, Director of Radio Astronomy Projects, Department of Science and Innovation (DSI), South Africa, and member of the GGOS-GB, GGOS has the opportunity, together with the DSI and the UN-GGCE, to organise the event "Africa Rising: Shaping Our Common Future Through Geodesy" to be held on 27 September 2024 within the framework of the UN Science Summit 2024 in New York. The main objective of this event is to identify challenges and opportunities for the implementation of the UN Resolution on the "Global Geodetic Reference Frame for Sustainable Development" in Africa. This meeting

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is also the starting point for the establishment of the Affiliate GGOS Africa. A detailed report on the results of this meeting is in preparation.

As we conclude this foreword, we would like to express our sincere gratitude to all the colleagues involved in GGOS whose tireless efforts have contributed to the achievements summarised in this report. Together we look forward to another year of progress.

Sincerely,

*Laura Sánchez, President of GGOS, Technische Universität München, Deutsches Geodätisches
Forschungsinstitut (DGFI-TUM), Germany*

Anna Riddell, Vice President of GGOS, Geoscience Australia, Australia.

GGOS Coordinating Office

Director: **Martin Sehnal** (BEV, Austria)
Web and Social Media Manager: **Helmut Klima** (BEV, Austria)
Assistant: **Lucas Triebenbacher** (BEV, Austria)

The GGOS Coordinating Office (CO) serves as the Secretariat of GGOS and is hosted by the Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying (BEV – Bundesamt für Eich- und Vermessungswesen) in Vienna, Austria. In general, the CO coordinates the administrative work in support of the various GGOS structural elements, and is responsible for outreach and communications. It ensures information flow, maintains documentation of the GGOS activities, and manages specific assistance functions that enhance the administrative coordination across all areas of GGOS, including inter-services coordination and support for meeting and workshops. The CO, in its long-term coordination role, ensures that the GGOS components contribute to GGOS in a consistent and continuous manner. The CO also maintains, manages, and coordinates the GGOS web and social media presence.

This report summarizes the present status and progress of the CO, including the following GGOS associated components:

- Office of External Relations (Manager of External Relations: Allison Craddock)
- Committee “DOI’s for Geodetic Data Sets” (Chair: Kirsten Elger)

Present Status and Progress

The major activities and progress of the CO are summarized below:

- **GGOS Video Production:** The CO produced a 10 minute video about “Terrestrial Reference Frames” in 12 languages (<https://youtu.be/vvNXv05646M>) which was published in September 2023 and was viewed more than 46,000 times (all versions together). In addition, the CO collaborated with the UN-GGCE and produced a short version (2.5 minutes) targeting a more general audience and politicians (<https://youtu.be/zfqq-0d2txk>).
- **UN-GGCE Collaboration:** The CO has been meeting with the UN-GGCE on a monthly basis since November 2023 to share information about planned outreach activities, avoid duplication of work and work on joint projects.
- **Social Media Campaigns** were successfully carried out for the AGU Fall Meeting 2023 and the EGU General Assembly 2024.
- **Organization of GGOS Meetings:** GGOS GB meeting (22 Apr. 2023, 14 April 2024, Vienna), GGOS Days 2023 (20-22 Sep., Alcalá de Hénarés) and 2024 (10-11 Oct., Potsdam) and GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere (7-9 Oct. 2024, Potsdam)
- **GGOS Portal - Feasibility Study:** Together with the Vienna University of Technology (TU Wien), the CO has carried out a feasibility study to examine the realization of such a portal. (Bachelor thesis by Lena Steiner: [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10255995](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10255995)).
- **IAG Secretariat at BEV:** Building on recent successes of the GGOS CO at BEV, the IAG suggested creating a new IAG Secretariat at BEV. In April 2024, the IAG and BEV signed a memorandum of

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understanding to initiate this. All outreach activities of the IAG Communication and Outreach Branch (COB) and the long-term activities of the IAG Office will be handled together with the GGOS CO at BEV in future. This will make it easier to work together with GGOS CO and avoid duplication of tasks. The Director of GGOS CO will then also act as the Executive Secretary of the IAG.

Planned Actions and Milestones

Beside of the day-to day activities of serving as a Secretariat of GGOS and the support of other GGOS components, the leaded planned actions by the GGOS Coordinating Office are defined in the GGOS Implementation Plan (GGOS IP) as follows:

GGOS Portal and Internet Presence:

- **Unify IAG and GGOS websites and social media channels (2024-2025) [GGOS IP 4.4.a].** This includes the development of an integrated, harmonized website for IAG and GGOS accessible via the new domain geodesy.science, and the merging of the IAG and GGOS social media channels.
- **GGOS Portal:** Definition and implementation of the basic functionalities of the GGOS Portal (2025/2026) [GGOS IP 4.4.d]. This includes an operational web platform for the GGOS portal, the inclusion of all available geodetic product metadata integrated in the GGOS portal and promotional campaigns to encourage data providers to generate metadata for their products.
- **Expansion of descriptions on the GGOS website:** Inclusion on the GGOS website of descriptions of geodetic products and observations not covered by the IAG Services [GGOS IP 4.4.c]
- **GGOS Website Updates:** Revision and update of the GGOS webpage contents regularly (continuous) [GGOS IP 4.4.b].

Outreach and communication materials:

- **Popularize the importance of geodesy** (observations, products, community) and the IAG Services through the GGOS webpage, videos, and social media campaigns (continuous) [GGOS IP 2.1.a]
 - **One new GGOS video a year**
 - **Continuous social media posts** on GGOS and IAG related activities
 - Four dedicated **social media campaigns** a year on geodetic products (every three months a different geodetic product will be promoted through social media posts)
 - **Statistics** on the website or in social media
- **Creation of Factsheets:** Compile the observation and product descriptions in ggos.org into summary factsheets that can be made available online to everyone through GGOS and can also be translated into national languages by appropriate national agencies. (continuous) [GGOS IP 2.1.c]. The plan is to create four Factsheets a year.

GGOS External Relations Office

Manager of External Relations: **Allison Craddock** (NASA JPL, California Institute of Technology, USA) -- with support from the GGOS Coordinating Office, GGOS Executive Committee, and GGOS Focus Area leadership. The position of Manager of External Relations resides within the GGOS Coordinating Office. The Manager of External Relations coordinates, in consultation with the GGOS President, GGOS engagement with external organizations. The vision of the International Association of Geodesy's Global Geodetic Observing

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System (GGOS) is “Advancing our understanding of the dynamic Earth system by quantifying our planet’s changes in space and time.” This mission, as well as work toward the goals and objectives of the GGOS Strategic Plan, is partly supported by targeted engagement with external stakeholders, managed as a component of the GGOS Coordinating Office. GGOS External Relations includes a work portfolio that focuses on advocacy, visibility, and collaboration to ensure geodesy is a visible, valued, and sustainable worldwide asset. Working toward proactive engagement with the broader Earth observations community, GGOS external outreach and engagement centers on advocacy for interoperable, discoverable, and openly available geospatial data; promoting infrastructure development; identifying geodetic contributions to United Nations frameworks, as well as working with external partners to leverage the use of geodesy in broader Earth Observations campaigns

Present Status and Progress

GGOS participation in diverse stakeholder organizations works to identify synergies, making connections across organizations in the name of geodesy and mutual benefit. GGOS participation and leadership – often on behalf of the IAG – works to ensure Earth observation organizations are aware of their dependency on geodetic infrastructure for applications such as climate change and disaster risk reduction will be discussed.

GGOS External Relations has collaborated with the GGOS Coordinating Office Communications Team, as well as GGOS Executive Committee, to support collaborations with the United Nations Global Geodetic Center of Excellence in Bonn, Germany. Since collaborations commenced in mid-2023, the following outputs have been achieved:

- The GGOS informative video on “Terrestrial Reference Frames” was condensed, re-scoped, and re-written in collaboration with the GGCE in order to best communicate the essential role of terrestrial reference frames to policy makers, diplomats, and the general public. Craddock served as English language editor and narrator;
- Feedback to the GGCE was provided for the following documents:
 - Global Geodesy Needs Assessment
 - Hidden Risk Report
 - First Joint Development Plan for Global Geodesy

GGOS External Relations maintains contacts in numerous Earth observations stakeholder groups, and plays an active role in the Group on Earth Observations (GEO) by serving on behalf of the International Association of Geodesy on the GEO Programme Board (the international steering committee responsible for shaping GEO’s work portfolio). Through this and the GEO Disaster Risk Reduction Working Group, GGOS has been able to ensure that geodesy and terrestrial reference frames were mentioned in a major policy brief co-authored by GEO and the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. This policy brief, titled “Realizing Early Warnings for All: Innovation and Technology in support of Risk-Informed Climate Resilience Policy and Action” will be published in the latter half of 2024. This will be the first of four such policy briefs centering on the four pillars of the UN’s Early Warnings for All initiative, with future

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opportunities for highlighting the essential role of geodesy and reference frames in these forthcoming documents already established.

Planned Actions and Milestones

Looking forward, GGOS External Relations plans to continue active collaborations with the UN GGCE and GEO, with periodic interactions with CEOS and the ITU's AI for Natural Disaster Management focus group.

Specific interactions with GEO will include future contributions to international policy briefs, and participating in the development of the GEO Work Programme for its Post-2025 Strategy, including an Implementation Plan working toward integrated, innovative, and co-designed open Earth observations products and services. In its role supporting the GEO "Geodesy for the Sendai Framework" Pilot Initiative, GGOS will support an upcoming strategy and working meeting to be held in conjunction with GGOS Geohazards, IUGG, the Pacific Geospatial Surveying Council, and other Asia-Pacific stakeholder groups such as the United Nations International Committee on GNSS, and Regional Committee of the United Nations Global Geospatial Information Management for Asia and the Pacific.

GGOS anticipates continued participation with the UN GGCE for finalizing the First Joint Development Plan for Global Geodesy, and leading a significant number of actions described therein.

GGOS Committee on "DOI's for Geodetic Data Sets"

Chair: **Kirsten Elger** (GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Germany)

Present Status and Progress

With the 28th IUGG General Assembly in Berlin (11-20 July 2023) the status of the "Working Group on digital object identifier (DOI) for geodetic data (GGOS DOI WG) was changed to the permanent "Committee on Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for Geodetic Data Sets" (GGOS DOI Committee). This includes the participation of the chair of the committee as full member of the GGOS Governing Board Board (GB).

The main goal for the GGOS Committee on DOIs for geodetic data was the preparation of the Metadata Recommendations for Geodetic Datasets – part 1: GNSS Data. The draft document was introduced during the GB meeting 2023, and shared with the working group members and the co-chairs of the IGS Infrastructure Committee. A [revised version](#) was presented during the AGU2023 meeting with a call for public comments. The document is now in the final revision phase and a first version is planned to be published by the end of 2024.

The work of the GGOS DOI Committee was and will be presented during the following meetings: EGU General Assembly (2023, 2024), 28th IUGG General Assembly (invited talk and a dedicated side meeting to reach out to the community), IGS Governing Board Meetings (GB64 10-11 July 2023, Potsdam; GB66 30 June 2024, Bern), AGU2023, 13th IVS General Meeting & 25th Anniversary (invited talk, 4-9 March 2024, Tsukuba), and the GGHS (4-8 Sep 2024, Thessaloniki). Timely correlated with the 13th IVS General Meeting,

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the chair of the GGOS DOI Committee participated and presented the Committee in the annual GGOS Japan meeting and a dedicated DOI workshop for geodetic data for Japanese institutions (11-12 March 2024, Tachikawa).

Planned Actions and Milestones

Planned actions and milestones for 2025 are to further develop the DOI Metadata Recommendations for other geodetic techniques and services and to initiate discussions on ethical aspects of DOI assignment. These mainly include the results of common practices that geodetic data products are often distributed via more than one data center or repository and that there are different approaches about the DOI assignment. The ethical question here is: Should a new DOI be assigned for all representations of the same data product or can the original DOI and publisher be conserved. Recent activities reveal the timely need for discussions and the development of guidance that can be agreed upon widely.

GGOS Bureau of Networks and Observations

José C. Rodríguez (IGN Spain) and Martin Lidberg (Lantmäteriet), with input from the Service representatives and Chairs and Co-Chairs of the Committees that report to the BNO.

Bureau

The new Chairs of the Bureau were elected in February 2024, after a fruitful period of service by Mike Pearlman (CfA).

This coincides with several changes in the Committees associated with the BNO:

- New leadership in PLATO and DIS
- Updated Joint Working Group: Metrology of Space Geodetic Infrastructure (replaces JWG on Site Survey and Co-locations)
- New Joint Working Group: IAG WG 1.1.1 on Genesis

The Bureau and its Committees have contributed to the revision of the new GGOS Implementation Plan, the basis for its future activities for the forthcoming 10-year period.

The continuation of the work conducted at the Bureau will be shaped by several factors, including the adoption of the GGOS Implementation Plan 2024-2034, the beginning of the activities of the UN-GGCE, the preparations for the Genesis mission, and the expected—but unknown—developments in the different techniques.

Tasks from the GGOS Implementation Plan will be chosen in order of priority and feasibility in terms of dependencies. When possible, activities that support the UN-GGCE will be prioritised, strengthening the synergies between the UN Centre and GGOS and the IAG. The future focus at the Bureau is foreseen to include: inventory and analysis of the status of the geodetic networks and local tie surveys; ongoing collaboration with PLATO; following the progress on Genesis, providing a common forum for the Services and WGs involved; exploring collaboration routes with the various Committees (e.g. DOI adoption and other data management questions).

The discussion of topics with strong commonalities across techniques will continue to be at the core of the Bureau (e.g. local tie surveys, data management, planned satellite missions, observation campaigns, geodetic site requirements).

Services

IDS

- 61 stations, 51 co-locations with GNSS, 29 co-locations with tide gauges.
- 4th generation beacon deployed in 62% sites; Starec C antenna equipped at 48% stations.
- Average 89% active sites over 2023.
- New DORIS stations commissioned in Greece (Gavdos, Sep 2023) and Mongolia (Ulaanbaatar, Sep 2024); Major renovation at Rikitea (antenna moved 21m + equipment upgrade, Dec 2023)
- The network densification objective is 70 stations.

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- New IDS Working Groups :
 - “Integrated Clock Corrections for DORIS” to deal with the behavior of the DORIS clocks, exploiting DORIS clock co-locations both in space and on ground.
 - “NRT ionospheric applications” to broaden the use of NRT DORIS data for ionospheric analysis (based on DORIS RINEX + DIODE orbits with 3-h latency).
- IDS Elections in Autumn to renew 3 positions within the Governing Board for 2025-2027: Analysis Centers’ representative; Data Centers’ representative; Member-at-large
- IDS Workshop (Montpellier, Sep 2024), at the "30 Years of Progress in Radar Altimetry" Symposium.¹

IGFS

Work continues towards establishing the International Height Reference System, whose objective is to provide an international standard for the precise determination of physical heights worldwide. The first proposal for the IHRF reference network consists in ~170 stations, coordinated with the BNO, IERS, BGI, IGFS and the AIG sub-commissions for reference frame and gravity field modelling.

- Computation of IHRF stations points in Italy and Greece with different approaches.
- Participation in the establishment of the new absolute gravity reference system/frame.
- The Services integrated under IGFS provided multiple updates on their activities related to various product developments.
- Gravity, Geoid and Height Systems Symposium (Thessaloniki, Sep 2024).² Proceedings to be published IAGS Proceedings Series.

IGS

- Site Log Manager: application to manage GNSS site metadata (available to other parties).
- Guidelines for Continuously Operating Reference Stations, for station owners and operators of IGS sites. Translation available in French, and a Spanish translation is underway (SIRGAS).
- Preparation of a Charter for the IGS ACs and AACs .
- The next IGS Analysis Center Coordinator will be an international collaboration led by NASA Goddard and Geoscience Australia, with contributions from GFZ and MIT.
- IGS Workshop and Symposium (July 2024, Bern, Switzerland). Presentation materials and videos available on the IGS website.³

ILRS

- New stations: Tsukuba (JAXA) and Yebes (IGN). Yebes will be a GGOS Core Site as soon as the SLR station passes quarantine (expected autumn 2024).
- Development continues at Ny-Ålesund (Norway), and upgrade works in La Plata (Argentina).

¹ <https://www.altimetry2024.org>

² <https://www.gghs2024.com>

³ <https://igs.org/workshop/2024>

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- Low cost SLR system (Omni-SLR) under development by a Japanese collaboration (Hitotsubashi Univ., The University of Tokyo, National Astronomical Observatory of Japan).
- About 40% stations meet the ILRS productivity guidelines.
- GNSS tracking continues to increase its share of SLR telescope time.
- International Workshop on Laser Ranging (online, Oct 2023). Videos available at the ILRS site.⁴

IVS

- VGOS products are currently about a factor of 2 better than S/X for station coordinates, and at the same level for EOP.
- Future observations schedules planned: twice daily intensives, several 24-h VGOS sessions per week, several 24-h VGOS and S/X CRF sessions per year, more R&D sessions.
- Santa Maria (Portugal) site joining VGOS operations; developments continue in Matera (Italy), Harteebesthoek (South Africa), Chiang Mai and Songkhla (Thailand), and Fortaleza (Brazil).
- Optimistic projections for the VGOS network up to 2030 show a doubling of the antennas deployed worldwide.
- IVS General Meeting & 25th anniversary (Tsukuba, Mar 2024).⁵

PSMSL

- Slight increase in the number of stations available in the last two years.
- GNSS-IR growing as a sea level measurement technique. GNSS-IR portal at PSMSL site.⁶
- The Service coordinated the IAPSO Best Practice Study Group on water level tidal analysis, with final document to be submitted to the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission.

Plans:

- Improvement of mean sea level dataset with higher frequency sources and better metadata.
- Development of interoperable metadata formats for tide gauge data.
- Allocate DOI for the dataset.
- Continue development of GNSS-IR portal.

⁴ <https://ilrs.gsfc.nasa.gov/lw23/index.html>

⁵ <https://smartconf.jp/content/ivsgm2024>

⁶ <https://psmsl.org/data/gnssir>

Committees

Committee on Performance Simulations & Architectural Trade-Offs (PLATO)

Alexander Kehm (DGFI) and Benjamin Maennel (GFZ)

Current Status and Progress:

- New lead, with Alexander joining as Chair (following Daniella Thaller).
- Splinter meeting at EGU 2024 and several studies related to PLATO presented at EGU.
- Updated inventory of PLATO-related studies and publications as basis for future plans.
- Examples of recently finished and ongoing studies.
- Simulation studies with respect to the new GENESIS mission and other potential co-location satellites (various groups).
- Simulation studies on quasi-error-free combination of space-geodetic techniques omitting classical local ties (Uni Bonn/DGFI-TUM).
- Simulation studies on future (spherical) geodetic satellite configurations and possible new co-location sites for SLR (Wrocław University).
- Simulation studies on future GNSS constellations and new observation types (GFZ, TU Berlin).
- Simulation studies on VLBI transmitter on Galileo (TU Wien).
- Testing optimized scheduling for VGOS (ETH Zurich).
- Studies on best integration of VGOS and S/X-legacy network for VLBI in conjunction with ITRS realization 2020 (BKG, DGFI-TUM).

Plans:

- Compile a summary of the main conclusions of the PLATO-related work conducted so far.
- Continue to encourage additional groups to contribute to PLATO.
- Plan Face-to-face meeting, tentatively attached to EGU 2025.

Committee on Data and Information Systems

Roger Fraser (Victoria Department of Transport and Planning) and Taylor Yates (NASA GSFC)

The new Chairs joined later in the year, after substantial reorganisation of the Committee, led in interim by Elisabetta D'Anastasio (GNS Science) and Ryan Ruddick (GA). The Committee goals have been slightly modified (e.g. transfer of the GGOS Portal to GGOS CO) and are under review, along with its ToRs and tasks for 2024-2028.

There has been considerable progress over the last few years. This includes:

- The Royal Observatory of Belgium (ROB) has worked with the IGS GeodesyML task force on improving GeodesyML's FAIRness for describing GNSS stations. ROB also implemented

GeodesyML GNSS station descriptions within its M3G GNSS station metadata system,⁷ operationally used within the European Plate Observing System (EPOS) and EUREF. In addition, ROB developed standardized metadata (the GNSS-DCAT-AP scheme⁸) to describe RINEX files, and implemented it in the API used to retrieve GNSS data from our EUREF data repository.

- GFZ implemented a web application for managing GNSS station metadata ensuring high usability and interoperability. It uses GeodesyML for exchanging geodetic metadata and is easily extensible, accommodating diverse use cases.⁹
- Geoscience Australia, through collaboration with Curtin University, undertook a second research project to identify and address gaps and missing elements in GeodesyML, how to better utilise contemporary international standards, and to propose a pathway to international standardisation. This report is finalised but is yet to be published.¹⁰

Plans:

- Reinvigorate and renew committee membership
- Revisit conceptual model requirements
- Re-envision Geodesy ML and maximize adoption

Committee on Satellite Missions

Roland Pail (TUM) and C.K. Shum (OSU)

Current Status and Progress:

- Evaluating contribution of current and near-term satellite missions to the GGOS 2020 goals.
- Advocate the realization of future gravity field missions.
- Support of MAGIC double-pair constellation, being composed of: 1) GRACE-C: polar pair, funded by NASA and DLR; 2) NGGM: inclined pair, funded by ESA.

Plans:

- Set-up a new concept of the Committee to increase participation by potential members.
- Advocate and support national and international space agencies in their processes towards future gravity missions, by providing/exchange available technical information, and propose to support/participate in missions studies towards their realization.
- Communicate with Chinese IAG colleagues to seek advice and collaborations to advocate for possible availability of Chinese gravity mission data to the scientific community.
- Continue exchange with PLATO on joint interests and possible collaborations.

⁷ <https://gnss-metadata.eu>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7777568>

⁹ Kindermann, J., "Development of an information system for the management of GNSS station metadata using GeodesyML", Bachelor Thesis, Hochschule Neubrandenburg, 2022: https://digibib.hs-nb.de/resolve/id/dbhsnb_thesis_0000002931

¹⁰ Ivanova, I., et. al., "Identification of gaps in current standards and strategy for mitigation", Project report, FrontierSI, Dec 2023

- Evaluate the impact of SWOT to IAG/GGOS products.
- Advocate and support Genesis.

Working Groups

IAG Joint Working Group 1.2.2: Metrology of Space Geodetic Infrastructure

Ryan Hippenstiel (NOAA) and Cornelia Eschelbach (University Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences)

The name of the committee was updated after desire from IAG to refresh it. New Co-Chair joining this year, with Sten Bergstrand stepping down. The update is a good opportunity to expand on new protocols, technology and sensors, all at the service of improving local tie determination and other challenges (e.g. deformation, monitoring).

Activities:

- Investigations on the stability of reference points of VGOS antennas at OSO (Chalmers Univ.Tech., Frankfurt Univ. App. Sciences).
- Local tie survey at Goddard, including all four space geodetic techniques.
- Local tie survey at Shimosato (Shimosato Hydrographic Observatory, Japan Coast Guard, GSI).
- Local tie vector measurement at Syowa (GSI).
- Technical developments for Deflection of the Vertical measurements.

IAG Joint Working Group 1.1.1: Genesis

Johannes Böhm (TU Wien)

Genesis is a mission of the European Space Agency (ESA), approved for launch in 2028. A satellite in a near-polar circular orbit at about 6000 km altitude will be equipped with a VLBI transmitter, an SLR retroreflector and well as GNSS and DORIS receivers. While ESA will realize the mission and set up a Science Team, there has to be and will be a close co-operation with the scientific community at large. Consequently, this joint working group on Genesis by IAG, IERS, and GGOS will serve as an open forum for the international scientific community to exchange ideas and information, and to work for the best possible implementation of Genesis and the exploitation of its opportunities.

Current status and progress:

- Terms of Reference as well as goals and objectives have been defined
- List of members and webpage have been set up
- First WG meeting was held on April 17, 2023 during the General Assembly of the European Geosciences Union (EGU)
- Second WG meeting will be held on October 7 and 8 at TU Wien

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- Getting an overview of possible contributions by the various groups to the analysis of GENESIS observations

Plans:

- Identification of possible scenarios for the utilization of Genesis for the improvement of the terrestrial reference frame
- Combined orbit determination of the Genesis satellite; among the strategies possible, the combination at the normal equation level will be investigated
- Set up and implement a work plan with timeline to make the most promising scenarios possible once data is available
- Review and investigate existing co-locations in space between GNSS, DORIS, and SLR, as well as VLBI observations to satellites
- Identify and investigate new scientific opportunities, which will become possible with Genesis

GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards

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Present Status and Progress

This report summarizes the present status and progress of the GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards (BPS), including the three GGOS components associated to the BPS:

- Committee “Contributions to Earth System Modeling” (Chair: Maik Thomas)
- Committee “Definition of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs)” (Chair: Thomas Gruber)
- Working Group “Consolidation of best estimate GRS based on the adopted W_0 of the IHRF” (Chair: Urs Marti)

The BPS is chaired by DGFI-TUM and operated jointly with TUM’s Chair of Astronomical and Physical Geodesy. Further involved partners are GFZ (German Research Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam) and DLR (German Aerospace Centre, Oberpfaffenhofen). The Bureau comprises the staff members, the chairs of the associated GGOS components, as well as representatives of the IAG Services and other entities involved (see GGOS website at <https://ggos.org/about/org/bureau/bps/> for more information).

Major activities and the progress of the BPS are summarized below:

- The BPS keeps track and fosters homogenization of adopted geodetic standards and conventions across all components of the IAG as a fundamental basis for the generation of consistent geodetic products. The BPS inventory of standards and conventions used for the generation of IAG products (published in the Geodesists Handbook 2016 and 2020) presents the current status, identifies gaps and provides recommendations to further improve the consistency of geodetic products.
- The BPS supports the IERS Conventions Center concerning the updating of the IERS Conventions. Thereby, the focus is on the updating of Chapter 1 of the IERS Conventions “General definitions and numerical standards”.
- In collaboration with the IAG and other GGOS components, the BPS has created user-friendly descriptions of geodetic products, which have been implemented at the GGOS website (www.ggos.org). The BPS also supports the GGOS Coordination Office in the development of the GGOS Portal that serves as a unique search and access point (one-stop-shop) for geodetic data and products.

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- The BPS contributes to promote geodetic results to other disciplines and to make geodesy more visible in the geoscientific community and beyond (Angermann et al. 2023). In collaboration with the GGOS Coordinating Office and the United Nations Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence (UN-GGCE), the BPS contributes to outreach activities in social media, e.g., through the creation of videos about geodesy and geodetic results in non-specialist language.
- Furthermore, the director of the BPS serves as IAG representative to ISO/TC 211 and UN GGIM “GGRF” Subcommittee on Geodesy (SCoG), mainly to the Working Group “Data sharing and development of geodetic standards”. The BPS also contributes to the activities of the Committee “Definition of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs)” and to the two GGOS Working Groups on “DOIs for geodetic data” and “Consolidation of best estimate GRS based on the adopted W_0 of the IHRF”.

Ongoing Activities and Planned Actions

The ongoing activities and planned actions of the Bureau can be divided into four main categories:

- **Coordination activities:** This category comprises GGOS Governing Board meetings (twice per year) and monthly telecons of the GGOS Executive Committee to ensure a regular exchange of information among the GGOS components and to manage the strategic planning and day-to-day activities. Furthermore, external and internal BPS meetings are regularly scheduled to coordinate and perform the operational Bureau work.
- **Unification of standards:** A continuous task of the BPS is to keep track of adopted geodetic standards and conventions across all GGOS components as a fundamental basis for the generation of consistent geodetic products. This task requires the interaction with the IAG Services, the IERS Conventions Center, the IAU Commission A3 “Fundamental Standards”, and ISO/TC 211. An important long-term activity is a regular updating of the BPS inventory of standards and conventions to incorporate the latest developments in these fields.
- **Geodetic products:** Ongoing BPS activities and planned actions are to generate further product descriptions (e.g. terrestrial water storage, time series of inland water, ...), to foster the development of new geodetic products needed for Earth sciences and society, to perform an accuracy assessment, gap analysis, and to define requirements for geodetic products. The latter tasks are related to the work of the Committee “Definition of Essential Geodetic Variables”. In collaboration with the UN-GGCE and the IAG Services, the BPS contributes to the mapping of the global geodesy supply chain regarding infrastructure, governance and product generation.
- **Outreach:** The BPS supports the GGOS Coordinating Office concerning the updating of the GGOS website, particularly regarding the description and representation of geodetic products. The BPS also contributes to the generation of GGOS films dedicated to specific geodetic products (e.g., terrestrial reference frames, geoid and heights) to make other disciplines and society aware of geodesy and its beneficial products. Furthermore, the BPS contributes to other GGOS outreach activities such as popular science articles, brochures, fact sheets, etc.

Reference:

Angermann D., Pail R., Seitz F., Hugentobler U.: The importance of geodetic reference frames – A uniform basis to tackle current and future challenges. *GIM International*, 37(7), 2023.

GGOS Committee on Earth System Modeling

Maik Thomas, Helmholtz Centre Potsdam GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences

Present Status and Progress

Recent activities of the committee related to the combination of data assimilation techniques and AI algorithms as well as on model error estimates have been continued. Foci were in particular placed on:

- Application of neural networks in system model approaches for mid-term predictions of Earth orientation parameters;
- Sensitivity experiments for the estimation of the importance of anelasticity in forward, i.e., unconstrained surface deformation models;
- Evaluation of simulated third-degree ocean tides by means of in situ measurements with superconducting gravimeters and estimation of their relevance in background models for the processing of satellite gravity missions.

Furthermore, the discussion on purposes (and disadvantages) of the implementation of algorithms based on artificial intelligence into numerical model components is ongoing. Due to its complexity as well as strategic relevance this will be an important topic also in the following years.

Planned Actions and Milestones

Planned activities in the next year will mainly focus on:

- Continuation of feasibility studies regarding the coupling of neural networks with data assimilation techniques and application of the combined approach in stand-alone models;
- Discussion of implications of upcoming new hardware architectures for computationally intensive system model simulations;
- Discussion of consequences of open sciences principles for the geodetic model community, e.g., in view of open access to model source codes, analysis tools, etc.

GGOS Committee on Essential Geodetic Variables

Thomas Gruber, Technical University of Munich

Present Status and Progress

The GGOS Committee “Definition of Essential Geodetic Variables” was established in 2018 in order to define a list of Essential Geodetic Variables and to assign requirements to them. Geodesy observes the Earth as a whole, from the interior to the surface, including the atmosphere, with regional and local refinements, and provides a large number of products for this purpose. Moreover, geodetic products are needed for all positioning and satellite navigation tasks, and thus play an elementary role in modern society. So far, however, these products suffer from a lack of visibility for the global society (non-geodetic

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communities, administration, decision makers, science and others) and in some cases they are also not easy to understand for non-experts. Therefore, these products are regarded as contribution of geodesy to Earth observation providing substantial information to a set of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs), which are crucial (essential) to characterizing the geodetic properties of the Earth and that are needed to understand the dynamics of the Earth system in all its components and their interplay. An EGV is a geometrical or a physical variable or a group of linked variables that critically contributes to the characterization of the geometrical and physical shape of the Earth and to its orientation in space. All essential variables shall be continuously monitored and shall meet specific requirements in terms of spatial and temporal resolution and in terms of latency and consistency. They are essential to continuously monitor the Earth system, to assess possible risks, to develop mitigation strategies and to underpin the availability of sustainable geodetic services.

During GGOS Days 2017 it was agreed that a Committee within the GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards should be established in order to define the list of Essential Geodetic Variables and to assign requirements to them. This Committee was subsequently established in 2018 and consists of representatives of the IAG Services, Commissions, Inter-Commission Committees, and GGOS Focus Areas. Between 2019 and 2023 an initial gap analysis was performed and first ideas about the definition of EGVs and requirements to them were developed within the committee and presented at various occasions (IUGG 2019 and 2023, GGOS days 2019 to 2023). After IUGG 2023 a white paper was written as discussion basis, where a first set of high level EGVs is described in more detail and where the links between EGVs and geodetic products are identified. After agreement by the GGOS and IAG governing boards, the white paper shall be completed by assigning and including requirements to the EGVs and publish them to the broader scientific community.

Planned Actions and Milestones

The planned tasks of the Committee on Essential Geodetic Variables are to:

- Conduct reviews by different GGOS and IAG bodies in order to reach consensus with all geodetic key players.
- Complete the definition of high level EGVs and the classification scheme (matrix) linking them with geodetic products.
- Assign requirements for high level EGVs and analyze if existing geodetic products meet these requirements or identify needs.
- Publish high level EGVs and their requirements to the scientific Earth observation community.
- Discuss the purpose of and needs for lower level EGVs, e.g., as a tool to assess deployed and needed geodetic infrastructure and update the list of EGVs accordingly.

GGOS WG “Consolidation of a best estimate GRS based on the adopted W_0 of the IHRF”

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Present Status and Progress

The main task of this WG is to define a consistent set of parameters and formulas for the definition of a new conventional Global Reference System (GRS). This includes the geometry (size and shape of a

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reference ellipsoid), the gravity field (normal gravity field of this ellipsoid), physical heights, terrestrial time and Earth rotation.

The new set of parameters is based on the four fundamental parameters: W_0 (Potential at Reference Level), J_2 (dynamic form factor, “flattening”), GM (geocentric gravitational constant) and ω (angular velocity of the Earth). All these quantities are well observed and monitored by various geodetic space techniques. Besides of the fact that the chosen parameters are physically meaningful, a further argument in favor to use these parameters was presented by Panou et al. at the EGU2024: They are less correlated among each other than to the semi-major and semi-minor axis a and b . Therefore, the derived parameters can be calculated with smaller formal errors.

Most of the defining parameters change with time. This includes seasonal variations and long-term trends. These changes are important and must be considered for the consistency of the ITRF (e.g. ellipsoidal heights). Nevertheless, in order to keep things simple for the user, this time variability will not be treated in the published definition of a new GRS. All quantities will be fixed to the epoch 2010.0. This is the epoch at which the W_0 of the IAG resolution No. 1 (Prague, 2015) is defined. All calculations are done in the zero-tide system. Only at the very end, conversion formulas to mean-tide and tide-free will be given for all quantities. In order to keep things simple, some very minor terms in these conversions will be neglected.

An agreement on which basic formulas have to be used for the calculation of derived quantities could be reached in the WG. The correct calculation of the derived quantities could be verified with three different independent software packages. Further work on the influence of the tidal system and the treatment of changes in the time system have been performed. A study on the influence on the normal gravity field is under way.

Planned Actions and Milestones

A draft version of a paper with the calculation of the parameters is available. It has to be finished and discussed in the WG. It follows more or less the structure of the papers by Moritz (1980) and Groten (2004). The progress of the work has been presented at the IUGG 2023 in Berlin.

The definitive choice of the numerical values of the defining parameters will be one of the next steps. For this, a large agreement in the geodetic community is needed.

The calculation of a new set of parameters is one thing. The main problem will be to convince the users to adopt such a system as a new global reference. Many users don’t see the necessity to replace GRS80, as they just see it as a conventional model for the conversion of geocentric coordinates or for the calculation of gravity anomalies. Main concerns are the danger of confusion and the necessity to update many software packages. This discussion has still to be lead.

Another question to be answered is the necessity to define a conventional global gravity field model. For many applications (e.g., global height system, reference for local geoid determination), the assignment of such a standard model would have some advantages. For different application we would need a low-resolution satellite-only model and a high-resolution combined model.

Focus Area: Geodetic Space Weather Research

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Present Status and Progress

The following items should be mentioned here:

- The EGU General Assembly 2024 as a hybrid conference was taking place in Vienna, Austria and online from April 14 to 19. The program of the Geodesy Division included the Joint PICO Session G2.7 titled as “Joint session on geoscience applications of mass-market GNSS sensors and ionosphere monitoring and modelling”. The main convener of the session was Balaji Devaraju. Co-conveners have been among other colleagues Ehsan Forootan and Claudia Borries (DLR, Neustrelitz). The session combined two key aspects of geoscience research. Firstly, the potential of global navigation satellite systems (GNSS) focusing on small and mass market devices. They are used in various geosciences such as geodesy, hydrology and meteorology. Secondly, the session addressed recent advances and future challenges in thermosphere and ionosphere research, with a focus on space weather modelling and forecasting. One objective of the session was to investigate the interconnected systems that influence total electron content (TEC), plasma density and the thermospheric neutral density.

The ionosphere and thermosphere part of the session included only 6 PICO presentations. Consequently, we suggest for the EGU 2025, which will take place from April 27 to May 2, 2025, to change the format of a session related to the Focus Area on Geodetic Space Weather Research (FA-GSWR) from PICO to the traditional oral and poster ones. The convener and co-conveners should be the Chairs and Vice Chairs of the Joint Study Groups (JSG) of the FA-GSWR including women and young scientists. The title of this new session could be “Geodetic Atmosphere and Space Weather Research”.

- During the 28th General Assembly of the IUGG in Berlin from July 11 to 20, 2023, we discussed within the FA-GSWR how to establish a Joint Interassociation Study Group on Space Weather that combines the activities of IAG and the International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA). We are right now working on the establishment of a close cooperation between IAG and IAGA on this topic.
- From October 7 to 9, just before the GGOS Days 2024, a meeting titled as “GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere” will take place at the “Wissenschaftsetage im Bildungsforum” in Potsdam, Germany. This meeting will provide an opportunity for all IAG components involved in atmosphere analysis to interact with each other and to meet colleagues from IAGA to share their results and identify new challenges in this important field. More details including a description of the GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere can be found at www.ggos.org/event/ggos-topical-meeting-atmosphere/. The motto of the meeting is “Bringing together science excellence to integrate geodetic and geophysical technologies for comprehensive monitoring of the

atmosphere (troposphere, stratosphere, mesosphere, thermosphere, ionosphere/plasmasphere) and the magnetosphere’.

- Based on the discussions during 28th General Assembly of the IUGG in Berlin in July 2023 we discussed the general objectives of the FA-GSWR for the current 4-year IAG period 2023 to 2027. To reach these objectives we rearranged the structure of the FA-GSWR and created 4 Joint Study Groups (JSG). They have been implemented into the IAG GGOS program and read:
 - JSG 1: Understanding Ionospheric and Plasmaspheric Processes
Led by GGOS; joint with IAG Commission 4, Sub-Commissions 4.1 and 4.3
Chair: Fabricio dos Santos Prol (Finland)
Vice-Chair: David R. Themens (United Kingdom)
 - JSG 2: Thermosphere Modelling and Applications
Led by GGOS; joint with IAG Commission 4, Sub-Commission 4.3
Chair: Guenther March (Netherlands)
Vice-Chair: Armin Corbin (Germany)
 - JSG 3: Space Weather Monitoring and Prediction
Led by GGOS; joint with IAG Commission 4, Sub-Commission 4.3
Chair: Haixia Lyu (China)
Vice-Chair: Benedikt Soja (Switzerland)
 - JSG 4: Atmospheric Coupling Studies
Led by ICCT; joint with GGOS FA-GSWR and IAG Commission 4, Sub-Commission 4.3
Chair: Andres Calabia Aibar (Spain)
Vice-Chair: Binod Adhikari (Nepal)

Other implemented IAG Study Groups and Working Groups within the IAG program will provide valuable input for the FA-GSWR, in particular from the Commission 4, Sub-commission 4.3.

As can be seen from the aforementioned list the structure of the FA-GSWR contains the JSG 4, which is associated with the Inter-Commission Committee on Theory (ICCT) of the IAG, the other 3 JSGs are directly associated with the FA-GSWR.

A detailed overview about present activities and future plans of the 4 JSGs is presented on the GGOS websites at <https://ggos.org/about/org/fa/geodetic-space-weather-research/groups/> and will not be repeated here.

- Finally, it should be mentioned that significant progress has been made in third-party funded national and international projects in the last time. These projects are often strongly coupled to the objectives of the JGSs of the FA-GSWR.

Planned Actions and Milestones

- In the previous 4-year IAG period from 2019 to 2023 the 4 groups (1 Joint Study Group and 3 Joint Working Groups) of the FA-GSWR worked very successful on many scientific pieces to reach the objectives of the individual groups. Thus, during this time the 4 groups worked mostly independent.

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In the current 4-year IAG period from 2023 to 2027, the work, in particular the results of the 4 groups from the previous 4-year period 2019 to 2023, will be linked in such a way that we get closer to, for example, the study of coupling processes and the combination of solar and space geodetic observation techniques; this includes also the comparison with physical models such as TIE-GCM. Finally, we want to better understand the whole chain of physical processes between the Sun and the Earth' surface.

- From each of the 4 JSGs we will need so-called 'Foreseen GGOS Products'. These products, such as global and regional VTEC or electron density maps should be finally provided to users. They should also be interchanged between to JSGs for joint activities, e.g. comparison studies.
- In the following years the FA-GSWR will continue working on the following aspects:
 - Extensive simulation studies must be performed to assess the impact of space weather events on technical systems and to define necessary actions in case of severe space weather events,
 - Development of ionosphere/plasmasphere models as well as thermosphere models (maps) as stated above as IAG (geodetic) products for direct applications,
 - Continuation of the work on the definition and selection of the Essential Geodetic Variables (EGV) in the framework of the scientific work within FA-GSWR,
 - Establishment of recommendations for the applications of relevant models, e.g., in precise satellite orbit determination, for collision avoidance, in space debris analysis, and for re-entry computations.
- In the following years the FA-GSWR will also work on following new aspects:
 - Plan to extend the investigation area within the FA-GSWR from the upper atmosphere to the lower atmosphere. This leads to an integrated analysis of the MIT coupling processes and the vertical coupling processes (co-operations with the new proposed Focus Area on Combined Tropospheric Products),
 - In connection to the vertical coupling processes, we will investigate the projection of climate change effects from the lower to the upper atmosphere (co-operations with the IPCC).
- Other planned activities are:
 - Special Issue to disseminate the results of the FA-GSWR, (proposal by Haixia)
 - Producing a GGOS film on the contribution of Geodesy to Space Weather Monitoring and Forecasting.

Focus Area: Geohazards Monitoring

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Present Status and Progress

- The Geohazards Focus Area (GFA) is focused upon the implementation of the IUGG 2015 General Assembly Resolution #4 to expand the use of geodetic techniques and infrastructure in mitigation of natural hazards.
- Since the establishment of GATEW working group in 2019 that was global in scope comprising 18 members from 12 nations, we refocused the effort into Oceania and rechristened it the GeTEWS working group, the GNSS-enhanced Tsunami Early Warning System. The working group now comprises 15 members from 10 nations (chart below) and is focused on GNSS deployments in Oceania.
- The GAR 2019 white paper articulates the role of GTEWS technology and the GTEWS 2017 recommendations in the implementation of the Sendai Framework. GeTEWS WG has focused on developing a proposal for a three-year plan to create an Oceania-wide, intergovernmental, multi-use, open-data and continuously operating GNSS geospatial observations network.
- Organized a joint workshop between the Pacific Geospatial Surveying Council (PGSC), IUGG GeoRisk Commission, Joint Tsunami Commission, the IAG/GGOS Group on Earth Observations Geodesy for Sendai Pilot Initiative, and the UN International Committee on GNSS. This workshop will be held Nov 4-8 in Suva, Fiji.
- CWU, a member of the GeTEWS working group, initiated a demonstration Tonga pilot project to install five continuously operating GNSS stations at each of the five major island groups that comprise the Kingdom of Tonga. As of this writing three stations have been installed and are operating in Nuku'alofa on the main island of Tongatapu, on the northern archipelagos of Vava'u and Ha'apai. The purpose of pilot is to demonstrate the feasibility of deploying a GNSS intergovernmental geospatial network broadly across Oceania. All three receivers have operated and log data continuously since deployment but as expected, telemetry to the outside world is problematic until such time as dedicated Starlink or equivalent can be installed.

Planned Actions and Milestones

- Continue the buildout of the Tonga pilot project by installing the final two of five CORS on the northernmost island of Niuafoou and the easternmost island of 'Eua. This effort will continue on through 2024. By so doing we fulfill the request of the UNOOSA ICG's Task Force on GNSS Applications for Disaster Risk Reduction by deploying GNSS to reduce, in this case, tsunami hazard.
- Hold the GeTEWS-Oceania joint workshop in Suva, Fiji in November 4-7 2024. The purpose of the workshop is to review and recommend a proposal from the GeTEWS Working Group to create the Oceania Geospatial Network. **All workshop sessions will be recorded.** The link to the meeting announcement may be found here: <https://pgsc.gem.spc.int/event/getews-oceania-2024-joint-workshop-4-7-november-2024-suva-fiji/> and the workshop expression of interest page for

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prospective attendees from both international and Pacific Island countries may be found here: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdu_ILiOymLDxt2iLLGd6AVWsbUqs9c1izKK16TxkP2jV3gDA/viewform . The primary elements of the proposal are:

- A “Suva Declaration” from conference attendees endorsing a three-year plan to create a coordinated Oceania-wide, intergovernmental, multi-use, open-data, continuously operating GNSS Geospatial network for GNSS-enhanced Tsunami Early Warning (GeTEWS), environmental monitoring, regional capacity building, and real-time surveying.
- Establish the GeTEWS-Oceania network deployment as a project of the Pacific Geospatial and Surveying Council. Create a GeTEWS-Oceania advisory group to guide development, operation and maintenance of the project, with membership inclusive of the nations and territories of Oceania. Specify Terms of Reference for this GeTEWS-Oceania advisory group, ratified and adopted by representatives from the nations and territories of Oceania.
- Draft 3-year plan for implementing Suva Declaration.
- Write a meeting report for publication as an addendum to the Suva Declaration.
- Write Policy Brief which embodies the concept of collaboration and joint analysis inclusive of all GNSS networks within the Oceania Region. Tonga Use Case as an example.

The GeTEWS Oceania Working Group:

Tim Melbourne, Chair, Central Washington University, USA

Allison Craddock, NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, USA

Elisabetta D’Anastasio, GNS Science, New Zealand

Viliani Folau, Ministry of Land and Natural Resources, Tonga

Bill Fry, GNS Science, New Zealand

John LaBrecque, Center for Space Research, University of Texas, USA & IUGG GeoRisk Commission

Andrick Lal, Geoscience Energy & Maritime, Pacific Community (SPC), Suva, Fiji.

Léo Martire, IGS Central Bureau, Jet Propulsion Laboratory

Basara Miyahara, Geospatial Information Authority (GSI), Japan

Adrienne Moseley, Geoscience Australia, Australia

Felix Perosanz, Centre National D’Etudes Spatiales (CNES), France

Michela Ravanelli, Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris, France and University of Rome, Italy

Lucie Rolland, Université Côte d’Azur, France

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Yuhe Tony Song, NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, USA

GGOS Focus Area on Artificial Intelligence for Geodesy (AI4G)

Benedikt Soja, Maria Kaselimi, Milad Asgarimehr, Sadegh Modiri, Mohammad Ali Sharifi, Santiago Belda, Fupeng Li, Lei Liu, Mohammad Omidalizarandi, Justyna Śliwińska-Bronowicz

Present Status and Progress

GGOS Focus Area on Artificial Intelligence for Geodesy (AI4G) was officially approved in May 2023 by the GGOS Coordinating Board. In the following months, the structure of the Focus Area with initially three Joint Study Groups was established. In autumn 2023, an additional Joint Study Group (JSG) was formed with the title AI for Geodetic Deformation Monitoring. This report covers the activities within the Focus Area after this initial establishment of its structure. The report focuses on tangible outcomes and joint initiatives. In addition, significant research efforts are under way related to the overall goals of the Focus Area, i.e. the improvement of geodetic products using AI and their evaluation. Several journal and conference papers have been published in this regard, which are too numerous to list in this report. Currently, AI4G has over 90 members, demonstrating the great interest of the geodetic community in this growing field of research.

Activities of the Focus Area AI4G:

- EGU 2024 session G1.3 “Data science and machine learning in geodesy” organized by five AI4G chairs. 22 abstracts were received, and an oral session was secured, which had very strong attendance.
- AGU 2024 session G004 “Applications of AI/ML in Geodesy” co-convened by the AI4G chair. This session was proposed for the first time, and it already attracted 15 abstracts, which will be presented in the frame of an eLightning session.

Fig. 1: Advertisements of the EGU and AGU 2024 session organized by AI4G chairs

- GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere 2024: AI4G chair involved in Science Team and chairing the session on “Atmospheric modelling based on artificial intelligence”

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- EGU 2025 session proposal “Machine learning for geodesy” jointly submitted by five AI4G chairs
- IAG Scientific Assembly 2025: Symposium "Data Science and Machine Learning in Geodesy" was approved and is currently in preparation by the AI4G chairs
- Special issue in the journal Remote Sensing: “Signal Processing and Machine Learning for Space Geodesy Applications” edited by two AI4G chairs
- COST Action proposal “Artificial Intelligence for Geodesy” (AI4GEOD) was submitted in October 2023. A large European consortium of 27 proposers was established by the chairs of AI4G. 61% of the proposers came from COST Inclusiveness Target Countries, 56% were female, and 74% were Young Researchers and Innovators. The composition of the network was very positively evaluated, although the proposal was ultimately not selected for funding.
- A re-submission of the COST Action proposal AI4GEOD is currently under preparation for the 2024 cycle.
- Talks at international conferences about the activities of the Focus Area by the AI4G chairs
 - Soja, B., Kaselimi, M., Asgarimehr, M., Modiri, S., Sun, A., Sharifi, M. A., Behzadpour, S., Belda, S., Liu, L., Śliwińska, J., & Omidalzarandi, M. (2023). Advancing Geodesy with Artificial Intelligence: Opportunities, Challenges, and Perspectives within GGOS. AGU Fall Meeting 2023.
 - Soja, B., Kaselimi, M., Asgarimehr, M., Modiri, S., Sharifi, M. A., Belda, S., Liu, L., Omidalzarandi, M., & Śliwińska-Bronowicz, J. (2024). Harnessing the Power of AI for Geodesy: Recent Developments within the GGOS Focus Area AI4G. AGU Fall Meeting 2024.
- Invited talks about applications of AI in geodesy given by the AI4G chair Benedikt Soja:
 - AI Perspectives for Geodetic Hazard Monitoring. March 13, 2024. ITU/WMO/UNEP Workshop on "Resilience to Natural Hazards through AI Solutions"
 - Artificial Intelligence for Geodesy – AI4G. July 19/20, 2024, Qingdao EOP Prediction Seminar
 - Machine Learning for Predicting Earth’s Rotation: Insights into a Dynamic System. June 6, 2024, University of Bonn, Geodetic Colloquium.
 - Geodetic Earth Observation Empowered by Machine Learning. February 27, 2024, ESA Φ-lab
 - Demystifying AI for Applications in Geodesy. March 12, 2024, NKG Science Week

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Activities of JSG AI for GNSS Remote Sensing:

- A kickoff meeting was successfully held with overview talks and topical discussions
- The JSG chair is organizing a workshop on GNSS-R, with a strong focus on AI, to be held in November 2024 at GFZ Potsdam

Activities of JSG AI for Gravity Field and Mass Change:

- A Google Group was established to foster active discussions among the JSG members
- Change in leadership: Alexander Sun and later Saniya Behzadpour stepped down as chairs of this JSG. Fupeng Li has taken over as chair of this JSG.
- Members of this JSG participated in the ISSI Workshop on “Remote Sensing in Climatology – Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) and their uncertainties”. Currently, a review paper on “Uncertainties of Satellite-based Essential Climate Variables from Deep Learning” is being written, with a focus on ECVs monitored by GRACE and GRACE-FO. Advancing uncertainty quantification in machine learning applications is a major goal of the Focus Area AI4G.

Activities of JSG AI for Earth Orientation Parameter Prediction:

- A kickoff meeting and several further meetings were organized with overview talks and topical discussions. An important matter of discussion was the performance of machine learning algorithms during the 2nd EOP Prediction Comparison Campaign
- Collaboration with the IERS/IAG/IAU Working Group on the Prediction of Earth Orientation Parameters (PEOP) in analyzing data from the 2nd EOP PCC sub-campaign, which is dedicated to evaluating machine learning-based approaches for EOP prediction.
- Invited talks about applications of AI for EOP Prediction:
 - AI for Earth Orientation Parameter Prediction a Joint Study group at GGOS, July 19/20, 2024, Qingdao EOP Prediction Seminar
 - Insights from the AI4EOP joint study group at GGOS, Sep 30, 2024, Alicante, International Workshop on Space Dynamics, Satellite Geodesy, and Numerical Methods.
- Two webinars on Earth Orientation Parameters Innovation and Insight (EOP I&I) were organized:
 - Junyang Gou: Recurrent neural networks and their applications for EOP prediction. Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pcbTavxUHbg>
 - Mostafa Kiani: Explaining the Causes of Polar Motion by Physics-Informed Neural Networks. Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MsEuDnabS1k>

Activities of JSG AI for Geodetic Deformation Monitoring:

- A kickoff meeting was successfully held. This JSG was established about half a year after the other three JSGs.

Fig. 2: Announcements of the two EOP I&I webinars

Planned Actions and Milestones

Plans of the Focus Area AI4G:

- Timely re-submission of the COST Action proposal AI4GEOD by a European consortium led by the AI4G chairs
- Organization of scientific sessions related to AI for geodesy at conferences including EGU, AGU, and IAG in 2025
- Encourage research in the direction of the objectives of AI4G, i.e. the improvement of geodetic products with machine learning, investigations into explainable and physics-informed learning, and thorough uncertainty quantification.

Plans of JSG AI for GNSS Remote Sensing:

- Organization and hosting of IAG GNSS-R Workshop, November 25-27, 2024, GFZ Potsdam
- Preparing a joint publication on best practice guides, guidelines, or recommendations related to the implementation of AI in GNSS remote sensing topics

Plans of JSG AI for Gravity Field and Mass Change:

- Complete the organizational structure of the JSG by selecting a vice-chair
- Organize a meeting to introduce the new JSG leadership and refine future plans

Plans of JSG AI for Earth Orientation Parameter Prediction:

- Organization of additional EOP I&I webinars
- Contribute to the expansion of the 2nd EOP PCC, with a focus on machine learning.

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Plans of JSG AI for Geodetic Deformation Monitoring:

- Holding a webinar to increase the visibility
- Special issue regarding “AI for geodetic deformation monitoring” in JISDM conference (<https://jisdm2025.gik.kit.edu/>)